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GLIS1, a zinc finger transcription factor, controls expression of insulin.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Diabetes is among the leading causes of death in humans in modern society, and is associated with loss of insulin production in the pancreas. We performed expression screening in beta islet cells of the pancreas to identify nuclear factors governing expression of insulin. We identified the Kruppel-like zinc finger transcription factor Glis1 as a stage-selective switch that controlled insulin expression. Enforced expression of Glis1 in two separate human cell types resulted in production of insulin. Activation of Glis1 or targeted pharmacological modulation of its binding partners is likely to rescue insulin production in diabetic humans.

Results

We studied total transcription in a HEK293 cellular system following expression of close to 100 separate GFP-tagged zinc finger molecules.

Only one, GLIS1 (far right) was able to transactivate expression of insulin (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Activation of insulin expression by GLIS1.

GSE76495

GSE156846

Next, we studied a second human cellular system engineered to express a zinc finger protein, GLIS1, in

Data from a second human cellular system confirmed that ectopic expression of GLIS1 was sufficient to activate expression of insulin in human cells.

Figure 2: Expression of GLIS1 in human cells results in activation of insulin expression.

n=3 TM5 cell line with doxycycline-inducible expression of GLIS1 (-DOX)

n=3 TM5 cell line with doxycycline-inducible expression of GLIS1 (+DOX)

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Description
3630	1.33E-06	1.3251	-4.834941	-6.41	7.96	INS	insulin

Discussion

We report here the discovery of GLIS1 as a nuclear factor that controls the expression of insulin. Small molecule activation of GLIS1 is likely a viable therapeutic strategy for activation of insulin production in humans with diabetes. Diabetes is a leading cause of death in humans; kidney disease is a second leading cause of death in humans, and diabetes is a major contributor to death from kidney disease, as well.